

CYBERLENINKA

BASE

OpenAIRE

Google Scholar

SHARQ FALSAFASI CERTIFICATE

OF PARTICIPATION

THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO

Khamzayev Sobir Amirovich

TERMS THAT ARE CHARACTERISTIC OF TRANSLATING

BETWEEN ENGLISH AND UZBEK TRADITIONS

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

2023-2024

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

